

**CENTRAL PRECOCIOUS PUBERTY CAUSED BY A HYPOTHALAMIC HAMARTOMA
IN AN 18-MONTH-OLD BOY: A CASE REPORT****Dr. Zahoor Hussain Daraz^{*1}, Dr. Adil Ahmad Mohand², Dr. Berkheez Shabir³**¹Consultant Paediatrics, Medicare Superspeciality Hospital, Srinagar, Kashmir, India.²Resident Paediatrics, Government Medical College Doda, J&K, India.³Consultant Gynecologist, Medicare Superspeciality Hospital, Srinagar, J&K, India.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Zahoor Hussain Daraz**

Consultant Paediatrics, Medicare Superspeciality Hospital, Srinagar, Kashmir, India.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18429196>**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Zahoor Hussain Daraz^{*1}, Dr. Adil Ahmad Mohand², Dr. Berkheez Shabir³ (2026). Central Precocious Puberty Caused By A Hypothalamic Hamartoma In An 18-Month-Old Boy: A Case Report. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 13(2), 182–185.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 29/12/2025

Article Revised on 19/01/2026

Article Published on 01/02/2026

ABSTRACT/ SUMMARY

Central precocious puberty (CPP) is the result of premature activation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal axis. Although CPP is relatively common in girls, its occurrence in boys below two years of age is of exceptional rarity. We report an 18-month-old male child presenting with penile enlargement, curly pubic hair, and accelerated growth, later diagnosed with CPP secondary to a hypothalamic hamartoma. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain confirmed a non-enhancing lesion attached to the tuber cinereum. The child was started on GnRH analogue therapy initially to prevent premature epiphyseal fusion. This rare case of interest highlights the importance of early recognition of the cause of CPP and early intervention in optimizing the growth and psychosocial outcomes.

KEYWORDS: CPP- Central Precocious puberty, HH- Hypothalamic Hamartoma, MRI-Magnetic Resonance Imaging, LH - Luteinizing Hormone, FSH-Follicle Stimulating Hormone, OPD- Outpatient Department.**INTRODUCTION**

Precocious puberty is defined as the onset of secondary sexual characteristics before the age of 8 years in girls and 9 years in boys. Central precocious puberty (CPP), which is gonadotropin-dependent, arises from early activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis. Hypothalamic hamartoma (HH) is a non-neoplastic developmental malformation that is histologically benign but can be clinically serious. It is one of the most recognized organic causes of CPP in boys. Cases presenting before the age of two years are particularly uncommon and pose diagnostic and therapeutic challenges.

CASE PRESENTATION

An 18-month-old boy was brought to our hospital OPD by his parents with complaints of rapid physical body growth over the past several months and increased penile length with the appearance of denser pubic hair. Parents also stated to have noticed behavioral aggression and hyperactivity. On examination, the child's height was 94

cm (consistent with a 3-year-old), and body weight was 17 kg (>95th Centile). Stretched penile length measured was 7 cm. Tanner staging was done, which revealed pubic hair P2, axillary hair A1, and testicular volumes of 4.3 cc (right) and 4.7 cc (left). The scrotum seemed apparently large, and the trans-illumination test was positive. USG of the scrotum showed a mild left hydrocele. On further general examination, no café-au-lait spots or neurocutaneous markers were observed.

INVESTIGATION

Detailed and relevant laboratory investigations revealed gonadotropin levels (LH, 4.5 IU/L; FSH, 1.6 IU/L) and elevated serum testosterone (622 ng/dL). These levels were quite high for the age and correspond to mid-late puberty. Prolactin, cortisol, and other hormonal parameters were within or near normal limits. CBC with peripheral blood smear showed severe anemia (Hb 6 g/dL), and the picture was Microcytic hypochromic. Ultrasound of the whole abdomen revealed normal adrenal glands and kidneys, with a mild left hydrocele.

MRI brain demonstrated a well-defined lesion consistent with a hypothalamic hamartoma.

Table 1: Summary of the biochemical investigations of the child with central precocious puberty.

Parameter	Result	Interpretation
LH	4.5 IU/L	Pubertal range
FSH	1.6 IU/L	Pubertal range
Serum Testosterone	622 ng/dL	Elevated
Prolactin	11.5 ng/mL	Normal
Cortisol (AM)	4.3 µg/dL	Low-normal
Growth Hormone	4.78 ng/mL	Mildly elevated
AFP	2.93 ng/mL	Normal
β-hCG	< 0.2 mIU/mL	Normal
Haemoglobin	6 g/dL	Microcytic hypochromic anaemia
Serum Calcium	9.8 mg/dL	Normal
Kidney Function	Normal	—

Fig 1: Showing enlarged penis and pubic hair in an 18-month-old boy.

Figure 2: General physical appearance of the 18-month-old baby, showing accelerated somatic growth.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

The differential diagnosis for precocious puberty in males includes several genetic syndromes like neurofibromatosis type 1, Sturge-Weber syndrome, tuberous sclerosis, etc. Precocious puberty results from either a central cause, which is gonadotropin-dependent, or a peripheral cause. Central causes include hypothalamic or pituitary lesions and head trauma. Peripheral causes, which are gonadotropin-independent, include congenital adrenal hyperplasia, adrenal or testicular tumors, and exogenous androgen exposure. The required investigation is targeted to demonstrate the real cause of precocious puberty & is decided after properly examining the relevant concerning features. In our case, we did a targeted investigation of Pubertal LH/FSH levels, USG of the whole abdomen with doppler along with an MRI brain, which confirmed the etiology as a hypothalamic hamartoma, and the lesion, which

appeared to be attached with the tuber cinereum. Hence, a central cause was established.

TREATMENT

The treatment aimed to downregulate the GnRH receptors was achieved by continuous stimulation & the child was initiated on GnRH analogue therapy (leuprolide depot). This suppressed the premature activation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal axis. Pediatric surgical/neurological consultation was done, and follow-up was advised. Iron supplementation was given for anemia. Thorough parental counseling was conducted regarding the benign nature of the disease, treatment goals, and the need for a long-term follow-up.

OUTCOME AND FOLLOW-UP

Following initiation of GnRH analogue therapy, testosterone levels are expected to decline with stabilization of growth velocity and regression of overt pubertal signs. The child will be followed regularly for the progression of his height velocity, tanner staging, bone age, and hormonal suppression efficacy. MRI brain scan will be repeated to check the size of the hypothalamic Hamartoma.

DISCUSSION

Hypothalamic hamartoma (HH) is a rare congenital malformation composed of disorganized neurons and glia in the ventral hypothalamus.¹ These ectopic GnRH-secreting neurons function independently of normal hypothalamic regulation, leading to premature activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis, making it a well-recognized cause of central precocious puberty, especially in male children. The lesion triggers pituitary gonadotropin release and subsequent gonadal steroidogenesis.

These histologically benign lesions may be clinically serious and sometimes present with gelastic seizures or behavioral changes with aggression.² Seizures were absent in this case; however, parents did report relatively aggressive behavior. MRI is a powerful diagnostic tool to diagnose any brain pathology, and in our case, it showed

a non-enhancing lesion at the tuber cinereum consistent with a hypothalamic hamartoma.³

The clinical features in CPP that may present very early are endocrine in nature. CPP that is secondary to HH often presents at younger ages compared to idiopathic CPP. In one of the studies, the mean age of presentation in males with HH was 3.7 years (range 0.5-9.4), though presentation in infancy has also been documented. MRI is the investigation of choice in CPP and is essential in boys, given the higher probability of underlying CNS lesions. In HH, anatomical features such as attachment to the tuber cinereum or infundibular stalk correlate with CPP presentation.

GnRH agonist therapy is the mainstay for treatment of CPP, including that due to HH. It continuously stimulates and effectively downregulates the GnRH receptors and ultimately halts pubertal progression. This preserves the potential of attaining adult height and is well-tolerated.⁴ In-case presentation is with gelastic or resistant/refractory seizures, surgical resection of HH is performed.⁵

Our case is remarkable for the extremely early onset (18 months), markedly elevated testosterone, and clear hormonal evidence of central activation. Early diagnosis and prompt therapy are crucial to avoid early epiphyseal closure, compromised adult height, and psychological challenges. Treatment with long-acting GnRH analogues is the standard of care and prevents early epiphyseal closure and psychosocial impact.⁶

PARENTS'S PERSPECTIVE

The parents reported being initially alarmed by their child's rapid physical/somatic changes and aggressive behavior. They expressed relief upon receiving a clear diagnosis and understanding the benign nature of the disease and that effective treatment is available to control the condition.

CONCLUSION

- Central precocious puberty before two years of age is extremely rare, especially in male children.
- Hypothalamic hamartoma is a key organic cause and should be ruled out with MRI in all boys presenting with early puberty.
- Elevated LH, FSH, and testosterone with pubertal response confirm central activation.
- Early initiation of GnRH analogue therapy is a critical step to prevent premature epiphyseal closure and psychosocial complications.
- Long-term follow-up is essential to monitor growth and pubertal suppression outcomes.

Declaration by Authors

Parent consent: Taken.

Source of Funding: None.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Kotwal, Narendra, et al. "Central precocious puberty due to hypothalamic hamartoma in a six-month-old infant girl." *Indian Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 2012; 16.4: 627-630.
2. Hypothalamic Hamartomas Evolving Understanding and Management. Nathan T. Cohen, MD et al, November 2, 2021; 97(18): 864-873.
3. Boyko OB, Curnes JT, Oakes WJ, Burger PC (1991) Hamartomas of the tuber cinereum: CT, MR, and pathologic findings. *Am J Neuroradiol*, 12: 309–314.
4. Heger S, Partsch CJ, Sippell WG (1999) Long-term outcome after depot gonadotropin-releasing hormone agonist treatment of central precocious puberty: final height, body proportions, body composition, bone mineral density, and reproductive function. *J Clin Endocr Metab*, 84: 4583–4590.
5. Li C, Ma Z, Luo S, et al. Surgical treatment of a hypothalamic hamartoma causing central precocious puberty. *J Neurosurg Pediatr*, 2013; 12: 151-158.
6. Carel JC, Eugster EA, Rogol A, Ghizzoni L, Palmert MR, et al. ESPE-LWPES GnRH Analogs Consensus Conference Group. Consensus statement on the use of gonadotropin-releasing hormone analogs in children. *Pediatrics*, 2009; 123: e752–e762. - PubMed